

КУЛЬТУРНІ ПРАКТИКИ

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LINGUOCULTURAL ASPECTS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS TRANSLATION IN THE CONTEXT OF INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS COMMUNICATION

The purpose of the article. The research is based on comparison, generalization and systematization of scientific information on the linguistic phenomenon of phraseological units. In the article we clarify the essence and peculiarities of definitions usage in the aspect of the competent approach of the business English language translation. The work specifies the definition of phraseological units, systematizes the frequency of their use in the field of English business communication translation. Here are considered basic methods of phraseological units translation of business English language. Particular emphasis is placed on the analysis of business communication as a new interpersonal communication, the specifics, structure and functions of which are caused by business relations between different countries of the world. New phraseologisms, which operate in business texts, are semantic markers of actual events and phenomena of economic, political and cultural life of modern society. **Scientific novelty** of the work consists in providing a comprehensive functional characteristic of language innovations and aspects of their interpretation in the field of business communication that arise in the process of business sphere evolution and the impact of business on socio-political reality. **Conclusions.** It is proved that there is a need to preserve the formal component of the official business text while translating and complying with translation strategies for the translation of phraseological expressions. It should be emphasized that when translating such a layer of vocabulary as phraseological expressions it is necessary to use special dictionaries to avoid intercultural misunderstandings.

Key words: international business communication, official business style, business language, translation, phraseological units, culture.

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Лінгвокультурологічні аспекти перекладу фразеологічних одиниць у контексті міжнародної бізнес-комунікації

Мета роботи. Дослідження полягає в зіставленні, порівнянні, узагальненні та систематизації наукової інформації щодо мовного феномену фразеологічних одиниць, в з'ясуванні сутності та особливостей використання дефініцій в аспекті компетентнісного підходу перекладу ділової англійської мови. У роботі конкретизується визначення фразеологічних одиниць, систематизується частотність їх вживання в сфері перекладу англійської мови ділового спілкування. Розглядаються основні методи перекладу фразеологічних одиниць ділової англійської мови. Особливий акцент зроблено на аналізі бізнес-комунікації як нової міжособистісної комунікації, специфіка, структура та функції якої зумовлені діловими відносинами між різними країнами світу. Нові фразеологізми, що функціонують у бізнес-текстах, є смисловими маркерами актуальних подій та явищ економічного, політичного та культурного життя сучасного суспільства. **Наукова новизна** роботи полягає в наданні комплексної функціональної характеристики мовним інноваціям та аспектам їх інтерпретації в сфері бізнес-комунікації, що виникають у процесі еволюції бізнес-сфери та впливу бізнесу на суспільно-політичну реальність. **Висновки.** Доведено, що існує необхідність збереження формальної складової офіційно-ділового тексту при перекладі та дотримання перекладацьких стратегій щодо перекладу фразеологічних виразів. Варто відзначити, що при перекладі такого прошарку лексики як фразеологічні вирази необхідно користуватися спеціальними словниками задля уникнення міжкультурних непорозумінь.

Ключові слова: міжнародна бізнес-комунікація, офіційно-діловий стиль, ділова мова, переклад, фразеологічні одиниці, культура.

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Лингвокультурологические аспекты перевода фразеологических единиц в контексте международной бизнес коммуникации

Цель работы. Исследование заключается в сопоставлении, сравнении, обобщении и систематизации научной информации по языковому феномену фразеологических единиц, уточнении сущности и особенностей использования дефиниций в аспекте компетентностного подхода перевода делового английского языка. В работе конкретизируется определения фразеологических единиц, систематизируется частотность их употребления в сфере перевода английского языка делового общения. Рассматриваются основные методы перевода фразеологических единиц делового английского языка. Особый акцент сделан на анализе бизнес-коммуникации как новой межличностной коммуникации, специфика, структура и функции которой обусловлены деловыми отношениями между различными странами мира. Новые фразеологизмы, которые функционируют в бизнес-текстах, являются смысловыми маркерами актуальных событий и явлений экономической, политической и культурной жизни современного общества. **Научная новизна** работы заключается в предоставлении комплексной функциональной

характеристики языковым инновациям и аспектам их интерпретации в сфере бизнес-коммуникации, возникающие в процессе эволюции бизнес-сферы и влияния бизнеса на общественно-политическую реальность. **Выводы.** Доказано, что существует необходимость сохранения формальной составляющей официально-делового текста при переводе и соблюдения переводческих стратегий по переводу фразеологических выражений. Следует подчеркнуть, что при переводе такого слоя лексики как фразеологические выражения необходимо пользоваться специальными словарями во избежание межкультурных недоразумений.

Ключевые слова: международная бизнес-коммуникация, официально-деловой стиль, деловой язык, перевод, фразеологические единицы, культура.

The modern world is changing rapidly and this finds its actual reflection in language. Cultural and economic relations link together all countries of the world. Business has a growing influence on the development of international relations, which, of course, goes beyond the borders of one country and leads to the need for interethnic contacts in this field.

Despite the differences of values in each of the currently existing national communities is becoming noticeable tendency to strengthen the mutually beneficial relations. Thus, communication in the field of business strengthens inter-ethnic relations and as a result becomes the most important socio-cultural factor of the present.

In recent decades, interest to the study of natural languages as a projection of the national worldview has grown dramatically. In the sphere of international communication, the problem of mutual understanding is put on the foreground.

Good knowledge of the language, including English, is impossible without knowledge of its phraseology. Reasonable usage of phraseologisms makes the language more saturated and even more expressive.

The study of phraseological units as linguistic units, the most vividly reflecting the national peculiarities of the culture of people – native speaker, seems important in connection with the desire for an adequate understanding of mentality of the representatives of this nation against the background of contacts developing in the field of business.

The composition and general characteristics of the text written in business English are influenced not only by the rules and restrictions that are inherent in English as an integral composite system, but also by the norms and rules specific to the language, which must be taken into account by the user. The problems of phraseological units are today in the aspect of the most urgent issues of translation and linguistics. Phraseological expressions belong to such vocabulary layer, which, on the one hand, occupies a significant place in the national dictionary of any language, develops at a rapid pace, is in high demand among specialists in any field of public life, and because of this, focuses attention of many philologists. But on the other hand, is capable to create some difficulties for the translator of special literature. Without knowledge connected with the origin, methods of formation,

classification, functioning, peculiarities of the phraseological units translation, it is difficult to carry out an adequate translation.

Actual scientific researches and issues analysis. Phraseological units which used in business communication and aspects of their translation have not been the subject of a special study as a linguistic means of expressing a status-oriented expression plan. However, the question of phraseology and business discourse has attracted the attention of many, both foreign and domestic researchers. In particular, such scholars as V. Teliya, M. Amosova, A. Akhmanova, Sh. Balli, V. Vinogradov, A. Kunin were dealing with the problem of phraseology research. As for the aspect of translation, the communicative concept of translation takes into account the peculiarities of translation as an act of intercultural communication. Such an approach is embodied in the theoretical works of N. Arutyunova, M.A. Shanaeva that are based on analysis of business discourse.

Selection of previously unsolved parts of the whole problem. Today, when the world is undergoing rapid economic development and international relations occupy an important place in the field of intercultural and interpersonal communication, the translation aspect in the field of business communication becomes extremely urgent and attracts the attention of modern researchers. Therefore today in the international communication the problem of mutual understanding is put on the foreground. Until now, phraseological units which are used in business communication and aspects of their translation have not been the subject of a special study as a linguistic means of expressing a status-oriented plan of expression.

Therefore, **the purpose** of this article is to highlight the peculiarities of formation, functioning and usage of English phraseological units in business speech, analysis of the basic methods of translation and translation transformations of phraseologisms during the translation from English into Ukrainian.

Achieving this goal involves solving the following **tasks**:

- 1) to analyze the theoretical positions of domestic and foreign linguists regarding the definitions of “business English” and “phraseological units”;
- 2) to determine the idiomatic and metaphorical degree of business language;
- 3) to study the lexical, grammatical, syntactic, stylistic features of the translation of phraseological units in business English;

The object of the research is phraseological units of contemporary English and Ukrainian language business discourse, which include both phraseological unities (standardized formulas, clichés), phraseological combinations (including phrasal verbs), and phraseological conjugation (idioms), as well as stable comparisons and pemiias.

The subject of the study is structurally semantic, cognitive pragmatic, linguocultural and also discursive features of phraseological units of business communication sphere

The statement of basic materials. In today’s world, a large information block of material for business English language is phraseology. Without the use of phraseologisms, it’s hard to imagine any business correspondence, contracting, even writing such a banal document as a resume is sometimes difficult if you do not use phraseological constructions in it. Phraseologisms and phraseological structures are

such elements without which business English will not be so effective. Therefore, we consider the business English language and phraseological units in more detail.

In the formation of persistent language expressions a huge role is played by the factor of human presence, since the vast majority of these expressions are associated with a person and with a variety of spheres of its activities. Sh. Balli argued that: “The original imperfection of the human mind also manifests itself in the fact that a person always seeks to inspire everything that surrounds her. She cannot imagine that nature is dead and soulless; her imagination constantly gives life to inanimate objects“ [3, p. 221].

V. Gak makes a significant adjustments to the Sh. Balli’s statement: “Since in the center of human attention it is herself, then hence its constant desire to describe the world in its image and likeness. Language anthropomorphism is not a remnant of primitive thinking, as some philosophers claim, but the general law of the development of means of nomination in the language“ [6, p. 274].

The language of business communication does not imply the presence of emotional vocabulary. It is believed that the language of business communication is literally that business people do not use idiomatic, phraseological and other means of expressiveness when communicating with each other, they operate only with certain stand-by terms that are specific to a particular business line.

With the help of phraseological expressions, which are not translated literally, and perceived rethinking, the aesthetic aspect of language increases. “With the help of idioms, as with the help of different shades of color, the information aspect of the language is complemented by a sensuously intuitive description of our world, our lives” [1, p. 15].

In the characteristics of stable English phrasal combinations, academician V. Vinogradov comes from the fact that «most people speak and write with the help of ready-made formulas, cliché. In the system of modern literary language, words, to a greater extent, function not as free, suddenly interconnected separate components, but occupy permanent places in the traditional formulas [5, p. 65]. With this opinion coincide the statements of M. Shanskyi that the main feature of phraseological units is reproducibility [12, p. 97]. These considerations make it possible for all commonly used words to be divided into two types: non-reproducible and reproducible.

The first type is a combination of words (phrases and sentences) that we easily compose in the speech process on the basis of a special perception and presentation. Such connections are not stored in the finished form.

The second type are expressions (phrases and sentences), which are assimilated in our memory as the finished units of language. Such phrases do not have to be rebuilt every time. We only reproduce them in the form in which they are entrenched in the language. Since reproducibility is inherent not only by a stable phrase, but also by a whole sentence (proverbs, sayings, aphorisms), there was a discrepancy in the views of linguists as to the subject of phraseology, and on its volume [1, p. 5].

More than 20 definitions of phraseological units are known in linguistics, but none of them has been universally acknowledged. Some linguists rightly believe that the definition of a phraseological unit is as complex as the definition of a word. This

complexity lies primarily in the fact that it is difficult for the word and phraseology to establish common features that could be attributed to each of them without exception.

Phraseologism is an independent linguistic unit characterized by the corresponding differential features. Such features for phraseological units are: 1) phraseological meaning; 2) component composition; 3) grammatical categories [10, p. 80].

Phraseological units should be studied not by themselves, not in isolation, but in close connection with other units of language. Coupled in the process of speech with words, phrases, they act as organic elements of a holistic communicative unit, take an active part in the formation of its content, give it a special expressiveness, bright stylistic coloring.

Business communication is an interpersonal, intercultural area of professional communication, which involves perspective, communicative and interactive levels of behavior, due to pragma-linguistic and pragma-psychological (interest, conflict, mutual understanding) characteristics of communication. Business communication, carried out with the purpose of effective cooperation of people entering into linguistic communication, and aimed at optimizing one or another type of activity, presented in two forms: oral and written, the latter includes treaties, orders, regulations, instructions, acts, agreements, statements, contracts, summaries, prescriptions to laws, resolutions and business correspondence.

English language of business communication has certain peculiarities which must be taken into account and must be observed when translating.

Translation of phraseology has given much attention in the theoretical work of modern linguists, in various types of tutorials on translation, including the translation of fiction, in many publications on the theory of phraseology and comparative linguistics. Therefore, let's consider in practice the translation of phraseological units in business English.

The translation of such expressions consists of two main stages – analytical and synthetic. An important role in translation is played by the analytical stage – the translation of individual components of the phraseological expression. And for this purpose it is necessary to be able to correctly define them, since they can be not only words, but also the phrases that are part of the expression. It is also important to establish in which semantic relations are components between themselves. The synthetic stage of translation involves the construction of components depending on the above-mentioned semantic relations and obtaining the final version of the translation of the complex expression [6, p. 43]. The phraseological units of the official-business style representing a prepositive and attributive phrase may encounter some difficulty in translating because of the diversity of semantic links between their members and the differences between the structures of the English and Ukrainian languages, as well as the significance of their components (especially if the definition is expressed by the noun) [6, p. 117]. Prepositive attributive phrases can be both two-component and multicomponent. Thus, the analysis of linguistic works of T. Kazakova, V. Karaban concerning the investigated issue allows us to conclude that in any case, in order to correctly translate the data of the phrase, it is necessary to

analyze the internal semantic connections between their components, taking also into account the wide context [7, p. 119]. The choice of the method of translation also depends on the lexical filling of the attributive group.

It should be noted that there is no single universal way of translating prepositive and attributive phrases. In most linguistic works distinguish the following basic methods of their translation:

1) **Calque**

According to V. Karaban, this method of translating phraseological expressions is used when the expression thus translated is quite understandable to the native speakers, for example: *to sit with one's arms folded* – *сидіти склавши руки*; *to pull sub by the hair* – *надерти чуба*; *price risk* – *ціновий ризик*; *share capital* – *акціонерний капітал* [8, p.43].

2) **Morphological transformation**

This method of translation is widely used, especially when the attributive phrase expresses a variety of adverbs. For example: *the bearer depository receipt* – *депозитне свідоцтво на пред'явника*; *retail price inflation* – *намічений рівень інфляції*.

3) **Concretization (compression)**

Concretization is a lexical transformation, as a result of which the word of broader semantics in the original is replaced by the word of narrower semantics.

Anyone sentenced to death must have the right to seek pardon. – *Кожний, кого засуджено до смертної кари, має право просити про помилування* [13].

As a result of the process of concretization the meaning of the word *seek*, the general vocabulary meaning of which «*шукати, розшукувати*» is transmitted with the harmonization of the context of this sentence and refined to the value of “*ask – просити*”.

4) **Generalization**

Generalization is a lexical transformation, the opposite to concretization, as a result of which a word with narrower meanings is replaced by a word with a broader meaning. Since the use of such a transformation can lead to a certain loss of accuracy of information, it should only be used if the use of the vocabulary translation of the translated word can lead to a violation of the grammatical or stylistic rules of the language of translation.

...inhuman or degrading treatment... – ...нелюдському або принижуючому...

The glossary meaning of the word “*degrading*” is “*принижуючий, деградуєчий*”. In this sentence there was an extension of the translation sentence by clarifying that human dignity is the object of humiliation.

5) **Translation by equivalent or analog**

The equivalent is a constant lexical analog, which exactly coincides with the meaning of the word [8, p.257].

The Resolution “On the Course of Economic Reforms” adopted by the Verkhovna Rada (Ukrainian Parliament) is a Pyrrhic victory over the common sense. – *Постанова “Про хід економічних реформ”, прийнята Верховною Радою, є пірровою перемогою над здоровим глуздом* [13].

As we see, during the translation of a sentence was used the absolute equivalent of the phraseological expression, its meaning and structure are completely preserved in translation.

6) **Descriptive translation**

Translation by transferring the content of the English translation into free phrases. A descriptive translation is used when the language does not have equivalents and counterparts, for example: *to rob Peter to pay Paul* – *віддати одні борги зробивши нові (взяти в одного, щоб віддати іншому)*, *to burn the candle on both ends* – *працювати з раннього ранку і до пізнього вечора, не горить* – *there is no need to hurry up* [10, с. 98].

Thus, during the translation of official-business style texts, we encounter many lexical and cultural difficulties, the reasons for which, first of all, are differences in the picture of the world of English and Ukrainian. The main reasons for the existence of lexical and cultural difficulties in the official-business style texts are the lack of correspondence of new terms in the language, the peculiarities of the ambiguity of English and Ukrainian words, the peculiarities of word formation and terminology in the English and Ukrainian languages, etc. The stability and precision of constructing sentences helps to easily recognize the transformations and constructions that take place in the texts of the originals and their correspondences. That is why, while exploring the translation of official-business style texts, it is very important to note which designs are most often used and how the material should be used in one or another situation.

That is why, it should be noted that in translation of English phraseological expressions dominate such ways of translation: descriptive translation and the method of calque – 65 %, analog method and equivalent method – 25 %, and all other types of translation – 10 %.

It should be emphasized that the actual feature of the phraseological units phenomenon in language is that being an integral part of the language, they develop and evolve together with humanity, and therefore, remain an actual problem of lexicology and translation as long as the language itself exists.

Conclusions and suggestions. Thus, in the course of our study, a series of issues related to the translation of persistent expressions in the business English language were outlined. We tried to give our own assessment to the discussion issues in the field of translation studies, in particular the problem of the need to preserve the formal component of the official business text in translation and translation strategies for the translation of phraseological expressions. In the process of studying the given question, the main problems and methods of the translation of phraseological units were considered.

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